

METHOD OF CONTROLLING THE TRAINING PROCESS OF LONG-DISTANCE RUNNERS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the training methods of long-distance runners and the results of experiments and tests. Effective means of training runners, quantitative indicators of physical development have been studied.

The increase in competition in sports competitions in the world practice of athletics requires the improvement of the athletes' training system. Training of highly qualified athletes running for a long distance is a multi-year pedagogical process, an example of improving sports activities from year to year. This requires the management of the training process with such factors as the organization of training at different stages of perennial preparatory processes, the correct planning of the volume of loads, the selection of the occupants, the ratio of capacity of the cardiovascular system, respiratory organs, lungs for life, physiologic capabilities. Long-distance running shiddati and the result of the sport are not only based on technical and tactical skills, but also, in a priority, go to the functional training of the athlete. Consequently, taking into account the physiologic value of the training load and

general and special physical training taqsimlash, the improvement of technical and tactical training cycles (micro-, meso-, macroscopic), the preparation of competition, competition activity, the maintenance of sports.

Achieving a high result in long-distance running types of athletics does not require proof of adherence to the technical and tactical skills of the athlete. But the main loads inherent in the training of those who are engaged in these sports are directly related to the functional state of the taqsimlash. It is determined by the the functional capabilities, the training process plays an important role.

Over the past years, the world's leading long distance runners have been participating in many different commercial competitions, including the Grand Prix, the Javahir League (Brilliant League). Of course, these competitions serve as some kind of ticket to the upcoming World

Championships, cup competitions, Olympic Games.

The final result of participation in competitions depends in many ways both on the technique and tactics of running. The tactics of running should also be of a certain degree of variety, taking into account the situations that often change in the process of running at long distances. In order to properly carry out tactical rowing, it is necessary, first of all, to carefully study the opponents, their tactical capabilities, strengths and weaknesses. Then it is necessary to chase them near the finish, if the opponent is very resistant, and the speed is not so high, then initially it is forced to lead. If, on the contrary, the runner is fast, but the endurance level is lower, it will lead to the fact that he tries to

slip out of the carpet by running him from behind at a distance, putting the opponent on the run at a high pace, and increasing the chances of his victory. But the main thing is that before applying this tactic, special physical training of the athlete is considered one of the important factors. Because, it also educates long-distance runners to feel the distance with time as they move through different parts in designated intensity zones. Still in runners, a training plan is developed on the basis of special physical training. We have developed standards for running long distance runners based on the razryad classification (Table 1).we have developed standards for running long distance runners based on the razryad classification (Table 1).

Table 1

Graph of running distances according to the norms of the raziad of highly qualified athletes running for long distances.

Ixtisoslik	Malaka	Yosh (yil)	100 m	400 m	800 m daq.	1500 m daq.	3000 m daq.	5000 m daq.	10000 m daq.
5000 m yugurish	Irazr.	17-22	11,8	52,0	1:58,0	4:08,0	8:48,0	15:12,0	
	SUN	18-24	11,6	50,0	1:55,0	4:00,0	8:30,0	14:50,0	
	SU	18-28	11,4	48,0	1:52,0	3:50,0	8:10,0	14:10,0	
10000 m yugurish	Irazr.	18-22	11,9	53,0	2:00,0	4:08,0	8:45,0	15:10,0	33:50,0
	SUN	17-24	11,8	52,0	1:57,0	4:00,0	8:25,0	14:50,0	30:50,0
	SU	18-28	11,7	50,0	1:55,0	3:50,0	8:10,0	14:08,0	28:00,0

The results of the pedagogical experiment on Physical Training showed different results in athletes, both on all indicators. But despite the fact that their Sports razryads are the same, their

organism, anthropometric indicators, functional states are characterized by their individual characteristics. Of course, in case of breakdown of the training process, the

coach should distribute the training load taking into account the above features.

Analyzing the prestigious competitions of athletes, we can see that the participation of our compatriots is significantly less. The low level of the results shown by our athletes in these competitions is one of the main reasons for the lack of training in different climatic conditions, physical training, technical-tactical, functional training and training

sessions, as well as lack of experience in international competitions.

In the study conducted by US 3000 m. and 5000 m. we have organized annual training sessions of long distance runners taking into account the above omillarni in managing the training process of distance runners.

As a result, the following sports results were recorded by the examiners of the experimental and control group at the local and international competitions.

Figure 1. The dynamics of the results of the competitions in the distances of 3000 m at the championships of Uzbekistan in 2017.

Figure 2. The dynamics of the results of the competitions in the distance of 5000 m at the championships of Uzbekistan in 2017.

As for the results recorded in the competition, min and max speeds are 15.56,26±43,3 and 15.40,8±24, respectively,3s.ga equal, the range of

individual indicators is 16,54 s.ni made up. While the average statistical indicator 15.55,2±45,9;15.32,8±38,5s.ga was equal (Table 2).

Table 2

Dynamics of change in the result of sports in runners at a distance of 5000 m from the control and experimental groups (±δ)

The sports result was recorded periods and stages	Experimental group (n=12)	Control group (n=12)
1 - BTД		
TD at first	15.55,2±45,9	15.56,26±43,3
TD in the middle	15.48,2±38,5	15.50,51±33,2
TD At the end of	15.32,8±38,5	15.40,8±24,3
2 - BTД		
TD at first	15.34,6±43,4	15.38,24±45,2
TD in the middle	15.28,6±43,4	15.36,24±37,5
TD At the end of	15.26,6±43,4	15.30,15±34,7
3 - BTД		
TD at first	15.22,2±50,1	15.30,11±52,5
MOTB At the end of	15.25,2±50,1	15.28,86±35,8
Autumn race	15.18,6±42,3	15.16,41±21,8

At the beginning of the second base

training period,the average statistical index

(15.38,24±45,2 s) from the initial index (15.30, 15±34,7 s) was 8,1 according to the results obtained from the experimental group athletes s.ga yaxsh better. The range of Individual indicators was also significantly reduced (17,75 s). That is, from the range of individual indicators recorded at the beginning of the first base period 0,48 s.ga it was less.

Individual results (min - 15.34,6±43,4 s, max - 15.26,6±43,4 s) range from 8,00 BTD athletes of the experimental group s.ni made up. The mean statistical index was expressed as 15.55, 1±41,3 C. That is, the average figure observed in the winter competition (29,02 s) from 24,16 s.ga yaxsh better.

At the beginning of the third period of basic training min-max indicators 15.30,11±52,5 s.from 15.16, 41±21,8 s.up to the intermediate (14,70 s). Average indicator 15.22, 2±50,1 s.ga was equal. So,the result (15.18, 6±42,3 C), which is shown in the summer competition, is 22,70 s.ga it was space.

In the light athletics in the experimental group 5000 m. the results of distance running were studied at different stages of each base training cycle (at the initial stage of training, at the first, second and third stages of preparation). During the annual training cycle, experimental meaningful (non-traditional jumping exercises and exercises to restore leg muscle activity) exercises were used in the

intervals between training sessions with this group and at the end of the training session, presented in Chapter II.

The results obtained showed that from the beginning to the end of the annual preparatory cycle 5000 m.ga the running speed grew in a progressive direction.

So it should be noted that the stage of deepening specialization is a long-distance runner, when the technologies used in the management of the training process serve the athletes to increase the results of the sport.

The rise in sports results in long-distance runners is due to the physical preparation in them, that is, to the degree of good development of qualities, and in the case of rest, to the fact that long-distance runners work by immersing all body organs. To do this, it was first expressed by the activity of the cardiovascular respiratory system and the central nervous system.

In the distribution of training loads, it is desirable by the coach to plan the annual training process, taking into account the individual preparation of each athlete, the technical and tactical aspects of the functional state. At the same time, taking into account the climate conditions of cities in which the main competitions are held, such as the height above sea level, omillarni, will have a positive impact on the efficiency of managing and organizing the training process.

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